
Real Situation of Construction of New Rural Resources in Vietnam River Delta

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Abstract:

Socio-economic development of rural areas in the Red River Delta is unsustainable, the efficiency of resource use is still low, reflecting: environmental pollution, labor productivity and competitiveness of many products are not yet comparable. is commensurate with the existing potentials and advantages and is still far behind in some rural countries in the region. Therefore, researching as well as giving suitable solutions to promote rural development of the Red River Delta is very necessary in the present conditions. In the framework of this article, the author only mentions some main aspects of the current state of rural production development in the Red River Delta and a number of raised issues, on that basis providing a number of solutions. to contribute to promoting rural production in the Red River Delta in the coming time.

Keywords: New countryside, rural, Red River Delta, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

The family is the nucleus of society, the birthplace and nurturing people, so the family has an important position and role not only for the development of each individual but also for society. currently in the implementation of economic and social functions, preserving and transferring traditional cultural values of the nation. At any stage, family is also the driving force to promote social development. The family is the root of the country, so the development of the family will have a direct impact on the country's sustainable development.

In the context of a volatile world economy, the country's economy still faces many difficulties, harsh natural conditions, unpredictable developments, the results achieved in the construction of a new countryside of the delta. Red River and North Central are the great efforts of the entire political system. The region's rural infrastructure system is increasingly completed, better meeting the needs of production and daily life of the people, in which the rural transport system is basically synchronous and ensured. seamlessly connecting from village roads, communes to provincial roads, national highways, highways, to meet the needs of transporting agricultural products in terms of commodity production. The school system at all levels has received special attention to invest in building and upgrading, which is an important foundation for the quality of education of the locality to be increasingly improved. The system of medical facilities has been increasingly improved, in which the high-quality hospital system has been invested a lot, has been meeting well the needs of medical examination and treatment for the people; the region's system of waste and wastewater treatment works is in the leading position in the country.

The rural economy in the region develops diversely, the specialized farming areas are increasingly formed, participating in production chains, creating greater and greater profits for the people. The people's material life is higher and higher, the cultural and spiritual life is increasingly diverse, in which traditional cultural values are constantly being preserved, preserved and promoted. The political system at the grassroots level is getting stronger and stronger, and the people's belief in the Party's leadership has been strengthened. In particular, in concretizing the national set of criteria for new rural communes, many provinces and cities have raised a number of requirements higher than the central regulations, including the introduction of the 20th criterion (out of 19 criteria in the national set of criteria for new rural communes), when considering and recognizing a commune that meets the standards of a new countryside, that is, there is no outstanding capital construction debt.

However, the implementation of the role of families in building new urban areas in the Red River Delta still faces many difficulties, confusion and shortcomings from many angles. Family itself also suffers many impacts such as the process of industrialization and modernization; urbanization; the socialist-oriented market economy makes it also change in both positive and negative directions. In particular, in the implementation of family functions when participating in general social activities, including the NTM building program. On the other hand, it is also necessary to see that the implementation of the NTM building is still a movement, form, and performance, so there is a situation of over-mobilizing the contribution of families in the Red River Delta; NTMs have not been built to meet the practical needs of families in the Red River Delta, and have not taken the goal of improving the lives of rural families as the core for implementation. These limitations really become a barrier that makes the subject of a family in the Red River delta have not been maximized and effective in building NTMs.

2. Literature review

Research on new countryside in China, author Xuefeng said that new countryside is the countryside with a lifestyle that is suitable to the economic level of farmers.

After this stemming from theory and practice in China, the new rural concept is mentioned more clearly than the rural development, improved livelihoods, clean and tidy villages, and communes. Civilized and effective rural associations (Long et al. 2009, 2010).

In Vietnam, since the implementation of Resolution No. 26, the 7th Conference of the Xth Party Central Committee on August 5, 2008 on agriculture, farmers and rural areas; On October 28, 2008 the Government issued Resolution No. 24/2008 / NQ-CP on the action plan, which emphasized the National Target Program on New Rural Construction. According to the spirit of the Resolution, the new countryside is understood as a civilized countryside, rich and beautiful, with modern infrastructure; commodity-oriented sustainable production; the people's material and spiritual life is increasingly improved; the national cultural identity is preserved and increasingly developed; the ecological environment is protected; Political security is maintained.

Later studies also mentioned the concept of a new countryside in the sense: a new countryside is a modern civilized countryside but still retains the beauty of Vietnamese tradition (Vu Trong Khai, 2009); the new countryside has a civilized village, clean, beautiful, modern infrastructure; sustainable production in the direction of commodity economy; the material and spiritual life of the rural people is increasingly improved; traditional cultural values are preserved, rural society with good security, democratic management (Vu Van Phuc, 2012).

From the above analysis, it can be understood that the new countryside is the countryside with civilized villages, clean and beautiful, modern infrastructure; improving livelihoods towards modern, sustainable production; the material and spiritual life of the rural population is increasingly improved; the national cultural identity is preserved and developed in a healthy manner; Political security is maintained and governance is democratic.

In Vietnam, the National target program on building new rural areas is one of the solutions to concretize and implement the policy of "three farming" in the spirit of Resolution No. 26-NQ / TW dated May 5 8 year 2008 of the X Central Executive Committee. Building a new countryside is not only the construction of infrastructure, support for production development but also a fundamental change in agricultural appearance. village; Rural residents' thinking and way of doing things can help them improve their material and spiritual life. At the same time, building a new countryside needs to achieve the goal of helping farmers remain attached to the fields and villages but have a more modern way of production, healthy lifestyle, comfortable spirit, their legitimate needs in life are increasingly guaranteed. Accordingly, building a new countryside is to develop comprehensively the economy, politics, culture, rural society as well as the political system, to meet the requirements of a prosperous

and prosperous rural society. democracy, civilization, develop harmoniously and keep the distinct characteristics of the countryside.

On the other hand, during the period of international economic integration, building a new countryside to help farmers have access to new achievements in different localities and countries, help people become active. be more creative, more creative, create a driving force to promote production and business development, and at the same time arouse the spirit of solidarity to help each other to build a society in a healthy, prosperous and democratic rural area more civilized and modern.

Thus, new rural construction can be understood as organizing rural space, architecture, landscape and infrastructure in accordance with natural conditions, topography, to maximize the advantages of the locality. The most effective way to develop the economy is to improve living conditions in a modern direction, social needs are guaranteed but still retain the natural ecological environment and the cultural identity of the locality.

Rural residents' contributions to achieving the set criteria and maintaining regular implementation ensure the quality of each criterion for the sustainable development of the countryside and better respond to the lives of residents. Rural people and country development. Sustainable rural development is understood as an economic, cultural, social and environmental improvement to satisfy the current needs of rural development without compromising the ability to meet the needs of development. development in the future.

Sustainable rural areas are reflected in rural economy, sustainable rural society and enhanced protection and management of natural environment (Tran Ngoc Ngoan, 2008). The main entity implementing these contents is rural residents. The participation of rural residents in the maintenance of 19 new rural criteria is also aimed at the sustainable economic, cultural, social, environmental, and inclusive development of the countryside, and the preservation of values. nature to improve the quality of life of the current rural population without compromising their ability to meet future rural development needs as developed countries do in the regional development rural areas (Pugliese, 2001).

Participation of rural residents in new rural construction

Rural residents in this study are those who live and work in rural areas, mainly farm households (usually the head of the household representing the household), which is the force that carries out the family economic development. , is the subject participating in socio-cultural activities, is the subject that plays an important role, decisive to the success and sustainability of the process of enterprise trade. The participation of rural residents according to the theory of stakeholders must be prominent (in terms of: power, legitimacy and urgency); According to the theory of participation, they should be empowered to promote their independence, autonomy, dynamism, creativity to serve their own interests.

The participation of rural residents in the construction of new rural areas has been mentioned by some authors in each aspect such as: rural residents implementing rural livelihoods, transforming rural livelihoods in the Andes and expanding their income (Bebbington, 1999; Cramb, 2004; Mather, 2006; Guo, 2009); farmers have created jobs by making full use of their resources, using capital scattered among the people,... to increase farmers' income (Long et al., 2010); Rural residents participate in the development, maintenance and protection of typical rural infrastructures and architectures by seeking their initial consensus and mobilizing cash or in-kind contributions from them (World bank, 1994; Bebbington, 1999; Laah, 2013); Rural residents participate in preserving traditional cultural heritage (Khamung, 2015).

In Vietnam, the participation of rural residents in the construction of a new countryside is mentioned by some authors in each aspect such as: the subject role of farmers (Phan Xuan Son, 2009; Pham Huynh Minh Hung, 2017; Nguyen Linh Khieu, 2017); young people to participate in building new countryside (Pham Huy Giang, 2010); women involved in the development of agricultural production, industry, handicraft, handicraft villages, and rural service activities (Nguyen Thi Anh Tuyet, 2016).

From the above analysis, the participation of rural residents in new rural construction is understood that rural residents have to perform specific jobs in the process of building a new countryside and benefit from the that activity. Rural residents need to have social responsibility both for the rural economy, a sense of protecting cultural heritage, protecting the environment, a sense of mutual love and responsibility with the community (Nguyen Xuan Thang, 2015). They need to be proactive in capturing information, contributing ideas, participating in decision-making, making decisions and they are the beneficiaries of the benefits from the new rural construction program.

It is necessary to have the participation of rural residents in the process of commercial enterprise registration because: all NTMs are related to rural residents, they are both the beneficiary and the implementer. The participation of the people will enhance their responsibility in developing a civilized and modern rural development; At the same time, it helps people to use local resources more effectively in family economic development in particular and socio-economic in general.

The goal of the participation is to achieve the sustainability of the NTM in terms of specific indicators such as: rational and strategic planning; modern development infrastructure, diverse, safe and sustainable rural economy, increasing income; landscape, clean and beautiful environment; a civilized and polite rural society, preserving the national cultural identity; always maintain security, national defense and social order, ...

3. Research method

Logical - historical method; summarizing socio-political practice; methods of information collection, analysis, synthesis (collecting documents, documents, documents, directives, resolutions of the Party, reports, statistics of the competent authorities, ...) issues related to the role of family, building NTMs.

- Methods of sociological survey include: Quantifying through 300 questionnaires of household heads representing families of 6 provinces (Vinh Phuc, Quang Ninh, Thai Binh, Nam Dinh, Hanoi, Hai Duong) Each province distributed 50 questionnaires; and qualitative through in-depth interviews (some officials and people) in some research areas.

- Research synthesis, document statistics to make comments and analysis.

- Analyze practical experience and draw lessons for Vietnam

4. The results of the actual state of building a new countryside in the Red River Delta

4.1. Experience in the world

In Korea

New countryside in Korea has really promoted rural people's consciousness to change their minds, promote the people's internal strengths to build rural infrastructure; production development, increase income for farmers. Initially, the Korean Government provided materials (cement) to each commune, while villagers put their own effort into implementing necessary village projects to improve their own living and working conditions. Next is the new village movement with upholding three main principles: diligence, self-reliance, cooperation. Thanks to the voluntary participation of the Korean rural people, the movement received a positive response and achieved considerable efficiency, the dirt-walled cottages were gradually solidified, the rural traffic system was opened. wide, the irrigation system was repaired, bridges were built, houses were converted from thatch to tiled roofs, more durable and safer materials were used to upgrade rural infrastructure; the fences around the house are renovated, neatly decorated to create a beautiful landscape, ... Rural people have regained their existing confidence to develop their own economy, build a a better life for each family, village, a stable rural society, national cultural identity is maintained and promotes good values, improved knowledge, a protected ecological environment. strong economic development (Park, 2009; Douglass, 2013; Looney, 2012; Pham Xuan Liem, 2014; Hoang Ba Thinh, 2016; Nguyen Tuan Anh et al, 2016; Tung Lam, 2018). Research results on new

countryside author Pham Xuan Liem (2014), emphasizes the role of participation of rural people through analysis of Seamaul Undong movement and new village model in Korea to prove that the institute Government assistance is meaningless without promoting internal strength; New village movement (Saemaul Undong) in Korea has been positively responded by rural residents: if the loan is included, the contribution of the people is up to 72.2% (Tung Lam, 2018); In the new village movement, the State supports 1, people contribute 5-10 effort and financial resources, people decide everything (choose all projects, prioritize projects to do first, publicly discuss, decide to decide the design selection, construction direction, and acceptance of the work). Specifically, Korea categorizes villages according to their development level and participation into 3 groups ("Grassroots Village" - A village with very little participation of the people, and is supported by improvement projects. improving the living environment and raising awareness of the people; "Self-help village" - A village with the participation of people (about 50%), supported by environmental projects, income improvement projects "Self-made village" - A village where 100% of people participate in the movement, are supported income improvement projects, cultural welfare projects), with the grouping like the Korean Government from scratch. 12% of "self-made villages" in 1973 increased to nearly 100% of villages nationwide meeting the standard of "Self-made villages". In the period 1971-1979, on average, capital mobilized from people accounted for 49.4% (Vu Nhu Thang, 2015). Applying to the Vietnamese situation is:

- Mobilizing voluntary participation from rural residents themselves in contributing resources to the process of commercial enterprise registration, especially in the period of raising criteria towards model NTMs;
- Encourage rural residents to participate in high-tech agricultural development projects or link production with industry and sustainable consumption markets.

In China

Civilized rural model: With the goal of building a model village with adequate and modern public infrastructure, especially roads, offices, sports areas, entertainment and service areas. The residential area is divided into chessboard plots for scientific planning and architecture of people's houses according to some typical types for rural houses according to the culture of each rural area, the houses with a large campus, modern architecture, Full, convenient for the daily life of people and connected with traffic and production areas and especially suitable for modern lifestyles. The fields were renovated, specialized in production, specialization was paid more attention. Each village has an enterprise that invests in production or processing of agricultural products. (Tang Minh Loc, 2016).

Three measures have been taken by China to increase farmers' incomes and improve underdevelopment in rural areas: (1) develop more profitable agricultural products through stimulus prefers to use innovative and distinctive varieties, developing a chain of links (from transportation, freshening, storage and industry); (2) increase farmers' non-farm income by promoting structural adjustment and institutional reform of village and town enterprises; (3) improve supportive policies and reduce burden on farmers (Long et al., 2009). "The localities all give priority to enterprises and cooperatives that have many advantages in terms of technology, finance, market, have good business plans, and implement effective linkages to consume products. products, increase income for farmers "(called top enterprise priority), along with that China has made mandatory conditions:" if businesses want to participate in agricultural production and building NTMs must invest in the stock market to ensure the capital mobilization of the business "(Tang Minh Loc, 2016). Farmers are given favorable conditions to participate in improving livelihoods towards advanced production, modern agriculture, and farmers to participate in the production of high-profit agricultural products (Long, 2009; Long, 2010).

Applying to the Vietnamese situation is:

- Create a mechanism for farmers to link with enterprises. The State should do a good role in legal terms to force enterprises and farmers to properly implement the responsibilities of each party.

Rural planning is really practical, feasible, strategic and suitable for all activities of rural residents with modern lifestyle and keeping the fine traditional culture of the countryside.

In Thailand

Like Vietnam, Thailand is also a traditional agricultural country, with the aim of promoting sustainable development in rural areas, the Thai Government has adopted strategic policies to enhance the role of people. People working in agricultural and rural areas such as:

- Agricultural extension and farmer empowerment

Farmers are given more rights to use agricultural land for production development: they can convert, transfer or lease or contribute capital to an agricultural company, but cannot change the purpose of use. land; They can also mortgage or pledge land use rights to borrow money from banks to actively produce, step by step change farmers' thinking and perceptions.

- Rural industrial policy

Rural industry is considered an important factor helping Thailand improve the quality of life of farmers. The Thai government has focused on restructuring the industry for rural industrial development, encouraging more processing plants and investing directly in infrastructure such as ports, cold storage, floors. auction and investment in research and development; industrial promotion and SME development, encouraging the use of resource advantages, combined with traditional skills, potential internal resources in manufacturing and marketing, ... and especially to focus on developing key industries such as the production of agricultural, aquatic and marine products for export and domestic consumption.

The policy of prioritizing the development of agriculture aims to improve the quality of agricultural products with a specific program "Each village has a typical, typical and high quality product".

The policy of "developing the processing industry", ensuring safety in agricultural production and food hygiene. The Thai government encourages organizations and individuals to invest in processing and farmers to take practical and effective actions to control the quality of food hygiene and safety for exports and consumers.

- Agricultural product price subsidy policy

Through the forms of organizing agricultural trade fairs, supporting and promoting product marketing, trade promotion, and branding, the Government of Thailand has helped farmers and businesses to participate. actively to increase the value and competitiveness of agricultural products; allocating and exploiting natural resources in a scientific and reasonable manner, thereby contributing to preventing the illegal exploitation of natural resources. At the same time, strictly and promptly recover the rural areas where natural resources have been degraded. For rural infrastructure, the Thai Government has had a strategic plan to organize the deployment and rational distribution of large irrigation works for agriculture. Farmers are encouraged to rationally exploit the irrigation system to develop large-scale agriculture, improve rice yields and high economic value crops and livestock. The rural electrification program with the construction of small and medium hydropower stations has been widely deployed nationwide, ...

To promote the active participation of rice farmers, the Thai government has other incentives such as buying fertilizer at a low price, free of fertilizer transportation, and provided with new high-yield seeds. Low-interest loans from agricultural banks, ... Besides, Thailand also provides price support for farmers to produce 5 main crops, namely durian, longan, litchi, mangosteen and rambutan. In order to implement this supportive policy, the Government has brought in senior experts in charge of the program with the task of monitoring from production, distribution, processing, price to finding new export markets (Ho Xuan Hung, 2016).

With the incentive mechanisms and policies of the Thai Government, the farmers have really promoted the active participation of farmers in the chain of sustainable agricultural products (organic agriculture, ...), trained farmers. farming techniques, technology transfer to participate in improving livelihoods more effectively.

Applying to the Vietnamese situation is:

Empower farmers. Create conditions for them to effectively use the State's rural development measures to expand production scale, apply science and technology and produce key agricultural products, with advantages in the direction of commodity production. to combine the development of the processing industry, modern preservation technology and the expansion of domestic and foreign consumption markets.

In Japan

- Complete and implement mechanisms, policies and laws to support the agriculture and rural development sector in association with the process of industrialization of agriculture and rural areas, promote agricultural technical innovation and agricultural extension. Japan has proposed the Basic Law on agriculture and nearly 30 other laws, at the same time many times amended "Law on agricultural land, Law on sustainable agriculture", ... With the thought of forming a complete system. In terms of law, Japan has created a legal corridor for rural construction and development to be conducted smoothly (Nguyen Thanh Loi, 2013).

- "Encourage the farmers to actively participate, attach importance to self-reliance. At the beginning, the construction of a new countryside in Japan played a key role ". In the later period, Japan was aware that "relying solely on the Government will not be enough, it is necessary to have active participation of farmers - the team of people who benefit in this work". Therefore, the Japanese Government has found ways to "enhance the activeness and creativity of farmers, so that they can really become the main army in the construction of rural development". Specifically, in the movement to build villages, the Japanese Government upholds the spirit of promoting creativity, daring to think and daring to do, from building and implementing the plan, to choosing products in the movement " Each village has one product ", all of which are the residents of rural areas based on their local needs to propose and implement. The Japanese government has developed policies to support agriculture such as "subsidizing agricultural products, building a risk fund for agricultural products, in which farmers spend 30%, ..." (Nguyen Thanh Loi, 2013).

Applying to the Vietnamese situation is:

- Perfecting synchronous mechanisms, policies and laws to help manage agriculture effectively, creating a legal environment for healthy, efficient and responsible agricultural production, trading, processing and consumption. responsibility with the community.

- Create a mechanism to arouse the initiative, creativity and independence of rural residents.

4.2. Lessons learned for the process of building a new countryside in the Red River delta

- To bring into full play the people's internal resources to realize the criteria in the process of building a new countryside, rural residents need to be involved in planning, deciding what types of works and projects should be prioritized. before, publicly discussing, deciding to design and supervising construction, and accepting the project (experience of Korea).

- Vocational training for rural workers, transferring technical advances, new varieties, science and technology to help farmers increase productivity of plants and animals, building specialized farming areas for goods, developing production to increase income. import and support to expand the stable and sustainable consumption market of agricultural products (experiences of people in the Central Highlands and the Central Highlands).

- It is necessary to create favorable conditions to encourage the participation of rural residents themselves in the jobs of new rural construction, they must be truly owned, the practical benefits of rural residents must be. pay

attention and create a mechanism for them to proactively develop their economy in the direction of advanced production, protect the ecological environment, develop infrastructure and improve the cultural and spiritual life in a healthy way (Chinese experience National).

- Need to promote self-reliance, initiative and creativity of rural residents. These characteristics help rural residents to participate fully, accurately and responsibly, creating good collective actions in the implementation of vocational training criteria related to their own interests (Korean experience , Thailand).

- It is necessary to raise awareness about the subject role of rural residents in commercial enterprise enterprises. They are the centers, are the direct implementers and direct beneficiaries and have a decisive role on the effectiveness of the implementation of the criteria and the sustainability of the national target program on enterprise trade (Japanese experience , the Southeast and the Mekong River Delta, the North Central Region).

4.3. Reality

Economy: A commodity production with a relatively high growth rate has been formed and developed. In the 2001-2008 period, the rural areas of the Red River Delta had an average economic growth rate of about 6.5% (the entire RRD had an average increase of about 7.3%). In 2008, GDP per capita and employee was estimated at nearly 11 million VND (645 USD / person) and 22.7 million VND (1,338 USD / employee), equaling 63.2% and 65.6% of the average rate. for the whole region is 1030 USD / person and 2040 USD / employee. Currently, the industry structure of households in the region includes agricultural households accounting for 56.3%, industry-construction households 19.6% and service households 24.1%.

Farm economy developed strongly, only in the period 2001-2007, the number of agriculture, forestry and fishery farms increased 9 times, from 1,646 farms to 14,733 farms. From 2000 up to now, production value and added value average approximately 4% and 3.2%. On that basis, the farm economy has made an important contribution to ensuring food security and providing food for urban areas in the Red River Delta.

In recent years, the application of science and technology in production has brought about remarkable results, the level of mechanization in general in agriculture increased from 48% to 65%, the level of irrigation. increased from 68% to 83% of the cultivated area is irrigated actively. In the last 5 years, the level of investment in agricultural electromechanical machinery in the region has increased by 2.8 times. The percentage of products mainly from plants and animals selected for propagation and intensive farming techniques in the region is about 70% of the production value (60% nationwide).

The structure of rural jobs is diversified, creating many new jobs every year for workers in the region. The rehabilitation and development of craft villages, many localities in the region such as Ha Tay (former), Bac Ninh, Ninh Binh, Nam Dinh ... has created quite a lot of jobs and improved income for rural workers. From 2000 up to now, the number of craft villages has increased from 367 villages to 654 villages with the number of regular employees increasing from 290 thousand to 457 thousand, on average, to create 23-24 thousand new jobs per year, contributing to increase the proportion of working time used by rural workers increased from 75.5% to 83.4%.

However, agricultural and industrial production in rural Red River Delta is mainly developed in terms of size and output, not commensurate with the potentials and requirements of the region. In some places, industrial zones (IZs) and industrial clusters (ICs) have been developed but have not promoted rural urbanization, and have not created job conditions for farmers to have land acquired, leading to industrial development. associated with stabilizing and improving the life of farmers.

- Social: The material and spiritual life of the people in rural Red River Delta is increasingly improved, the average income is about 725 thousand VND / person / month (512 USD / person / year). In the period 2001-2008, income was improved, helping to reduce many poor households. It is estimated that the rate of poor households according to the standard of 1 USD / day decreased from 48.6% to 23.2%. In 2008, the poverty rate

was about 8.5%. During this period, a number of other development indicators reflecting the living standards of rural households in the Red River Delta, such as the proportion of households using electricity, the proportion of households using clean water and the proportion of houses with permanent construction also increased. increased significantly, from 78.3%, 72% and 83.4% to 99.2%, 87% and 94.7%.

However, the lives of many households, especially farmers, are still facing many difficulties and incomes, not enough to meet the basic needs of living, education and health care of the household. The income of a part of farmers is still at the borderline of poverty, in addition to natural disasters and pests occurring, in many localities farmers can fall back into poverty. In particular, the proportion of trained workers is too low, affecting the ability of the working age to access jobs and improving labor productivity in manufacturing industries.

- Regarding environmental sustainable development: The development of industry and handicraft in rural areas, localities in the Red River Delta has created a lot of jobs for workers, promoting faster economic structure transformation. However, up to now, the proportion of industrial parks and industrial complexes having wastewater treatment systems meeting environmental standards in the region has just accounted for less than 70%. Many localities, due to the rapid industrial development, lack of attention to the prevention of environmental pollution, lead to the lack of waste treatment systems in many industrial parks and industrial complexes, causing negative impacts on environment. The situation of environmental sanitation in rural villages and communes is largely not guaranteed due to the lack of domestic wastewater drainage systems and the lack of waste collection and treatment systems.

- Regarding rural construction: The socio-economic infrastructure in rural areas has recently developed quite rapidly. From 2000 up to now, the rate of communes having electricity from 87.6% to 100%; the percentage of communes having roads for cars to the commune People's Committee increases from 87.6% to 100%; the proportion of communes with solid roads (asphalted / concreted) to the CPC increased from 42.4% to 81.3%; the proportion of communes having a cultural post office in the commune increased from 55.6% to 94.5%. The system of school facilities, commune health stations has also been built and upgraded much more sparsely than before, up to now, 100% of communes in the region have primary and secondary schools, of which 100% are primary schools. and 95% of the lower secondary schools are built solidly, the percentage of solid high schools accounts for 96%, the rate of communes with kindergartens is 93%. In 2008, 100% of communes had medical stations, the rate of communes having medical stations meeting national standards reached 82%, on average there were nearly 1.2 doctors per 10,000 people.

However, the level of modernization is still low, reflected clearly through a number of quality indicators such as the ratio of village and commune roads, the rate of achieved canal and canal lengths achieved low, not yet met. are required to mechanize production, narrow the development gap with the urban area. These limitations are mainly due to the lack of planning of construction, the lack of connection between the construction of infrastructure and the embellishment of residential areas. On the other hand, a part of households do not yet have the conditions to upgrade and build new houses, so the face of a new and modern countryside has not been shaped.

It can be seen that the construction of NTMs in the Red River Delta has become a sweeping campaign in the political system and the entire society, responded by a large number of officials, party members and all classes of people. Participation makes the rural appearance more and more prosperous. However, the process of building NTMs is still facing difficulties, due to the low sense of responsibility in some places, and the mentality of waiting and relying on; the funding source for the program is limited; In some localities, the income of the people is low. Criteria such as traffic, cultural facilities, and the environment require a large amount of capital investment, which hinders the implementation of the program. In addition, some communes have difficulties, with limited funding sources, and limited business mobilization, so it is also difficult to reach the destination.

Fig. 1. New rural road in Binh Nghia commune, Binh Luc district (Ha Nam)

Rural appearance, especially in the Red River Delta, after 9 years of implementing the construction of a new countryside has been renovated, spacious, clean and beautiful; The local infrastructure projects have been focused on investment and upgrading, have been well supported for the organization of production and living for people in rural areas.

With flat and wide terrain, and at the same time having a very early development foundation, the infrastructure of the Red River Delta is constantly being improved, most of the communes have basically achieved and surpassed much. requirement of standard.

The highway system from Hanoi radiates to the provinces, connecting with the modern and synchronous system of national highways, provincial roads and district roads, contributing to promoting the linkage of localities in the region. Rural roads have not only improved their surface, but also have full sidewalks, drainage ditches, lights, road signs, traffic signs,....

In most of the communes in the region, the roads to grow flowers and trees have been formed, contributing to creating a green, beautiful landscape and raising awareness of people in environmental hygiene. , step by step overcome the situation of littering the street.

Infrastructure requirements, such as: electricity systems, irrigation systems, rural commercial infrastructure, information and communication, residential housing, ... in the communes have basically been completed, meeting the demand. the rural people's increasing demand. In many localities, schools not only meet the basic requirements of teaching, but have focused on supplementing equipment to help improve students' physical abilities and skills; Village and hamlet culture houses are basically fully equipped with institutions, really a common living place of the people.

According to the report of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, many provinces and cities (Hanoi, Bac Ninh, Thai Binh, Hung Yen, Ha Nam, Nam Dinh, Ninh Binh, ...) have performed well in social mobilization. culture in the construction and operation of communal and village cultural houses, perfecting facilities for schools, medical stations ...

The Red River Delta is one of the two driving force regions for economic development of the country, with many favorable conditions for agricultural development from natural conditions to a long-standing development foundation and agricultural tradition.

Fig. 2. Development of high-tech agricultural production.

Promote stronger the subject role of the people

In order to successfully implement the New Rural Construction Program in the coming time, according to the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, the construction and implementation of pilot models plays a very important role, helping to summarize and discover ways. good work, creative ideas, as a basis for replication, creating spread to localities.

In parallel with the building of the pilot model, there must be a strong policy system to support the local authorities and people, and at the same time, attract the participation and response of all levels, sectors and the whole. society.

The role of key staff is very important, especially in the rotation and arrangement of key staff at grassroots. Reality shows that, at any place, the head of the party committee, the authority, the mass organization is really dedicated and responsible, regularly and drastically joining, will create a clear change.

The good promotion of the people's subject role in the construction of a new countryside is very important and has major decisive significance to the sustainability of the results of new rural construction. The motto "People know, people discuss, people do, people check, people monitor, people enjoy" is a guideline for the process of building a new rural sustainable.

In particular, the gathering of people's satisfaction when considering and recognizing the new rural standards has created a very good effect in the society, helping the authorities at all levels to have a foundation when deciding to recognize the standards / reimbursement. into the task of building a new countryside; Besides, the issues that people are not satisfied with are an important channel for the Party committees and authorities at all levels to come up with solutions, and commit to the handling schedule to ensure the sustainable new rural construction.

In the direction and administration of new rural construction, there must be a clear assignment of responsibilities to each level and branch; At the same time, if it is smooth in general coordination, it will create synergy. In addition, the strong decentralization to the authorities at all levels has created creativity in each locality, in which the leading role and participation of the district government has an important role in contributing to accelerating progress. and the quality of new rural construction.

The construction of a new countryside is not only mechanically subject to general regulations and guidelines, but also needs to be flexible and creative in accordance with the practical conditions of each locality. The creativity of each locality is an important foundation for the Central to summarize and promulgate general mechanisms and policies to be implemented in the whole country.

In addition, given the limited resources directly supported by the state budget, it is necessary to diversify the mobilization of resources from all economic sectors (enterprises, credit, contributions of the people, ..); At the same time, each locality should actively integrate resources effectively from other programs and projects in the locality to serve the construction of a new countryside. For the New Rural Construction Program, focusing on consolidating and strengthening the advisory apparatus, assisting the Steering Committee at all levels is an important solution to success. It is the fact that having a specialized and professional apparatus that bravely researches, advises, and recommends strong enough mechanisms and policies has contributed to speeding up the progress, quality and efficiency of building a new countryside in the locality. /.

5. Conclusion

In order for the construction of NTMs in the Red River Delta region to be more effective, in the coming time, the provinces and cities in the region should continue to give priority to promoting support for production development in the value chain to create high quality products and goods, increasing rural people's income; promote more propaganda about NTMs. The localities need to clearly define the central criteria to focus on direction, especially the criteria that reflect the quality of life of the people; continue to raise the standardized criteria under the guidance of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

The promotion of value chain linkages in agricultural, forestry and fishery production has been strengthened in various forms. In the years 2011-2016, the linkage of the value chain in agricultural, forestry and fishery production is reflected in the construction of large fields; contracting for product consumption prior to production; The linkage of capital contribution to production and sale of products of farms, businesses and cooperatives has also been focused and strengthened.

In addition, the credit and banking system has gradually expanded its operation network, creating favorable conditions for production and processing households to access credit. The market system serving goods exchange has been upgraded and renewed; support services are increasingly diversified and the economy has shifted in a more positive direction.

In the value chain linkage of agricultural, forestry and fishery products in the Red River Delta the main actors include producers, households, establishments and cooperatives; Collectors, processors and distributors are mainly households, processors, cooperative groups, cooperatives and enterprises. The highlight in the region is the association of households in building large sample fields, serving for deep specialization in commodity production. The association is done in two forms: signing contracts for the supply of raw materials, inputs and consumption of output products; and verbal contracts. The number of households, establishments and enterprises processing agricultural, forestry and aquatic products has increased rapidly over time.

The effectiveness of agricultural value chain linkages in building new rural areas in the Red River Delta is reflected in the restructuring of organizational forms towards diversification, value chain linkage, and production scale restructuring. in the direction of increasing the scale of goods, land is accumulated through the

breakthrough stage of land consolidation and building many large sample fields to serve the production of specialized goods according to the value chain, creating favorable conditions.

Mechanization and more favorable application of science and technology, improving productivity, quality and value of products. The subject also introduces three successful value chain linkage models in the area, which are the fresh cow's milk value chain link model in Ly Nhan district, and the clean rice production linkage model in Y Yen district, Ha province. Male and pork value chain linkage model in Chuong My district, Hanoi. From the current situation, the topic pointed out a number of limitations and the reasons hindering the improvement of the efficiency of agricultural value chain linkages in the Red River Delta region that small production is still popular, commodity production has not been Specialization; The role of cooperatives in strengthening and ending the chain link has not been really effective in many places, the application of science and technology and mechanization is still limited, leading to low production efficiency in general.

To promote effective agricultural value chain linkage, it is very necessary to involve the participation and efforts of many stakeholders in the chain. The thesis proposes four groups of solutions, starting from the starting point of the chain, which is the solution from the producers themselves, to the actors participating in the chain such as collection and processing facilities, from businesses, cooperatives and even chain actors such as technical assistance organizations, local and central government.

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